

Electrochemical Studies on Natural and Synthetic Hymatomelanic Acids

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Hymatomelanic acids isolated from four different soils as well as their synthetic varieties were subjected to electrometric titrations, both potentiometric and conductometric. The functional groups of the hymatomelanic acids could be ascertained on the basis of the breaks and inflexions of the titration curves. The titrations were carried out with caustic soda both in presence and in absence of sodium chloride. Baryta alone was also used for filtration. The titration curves, in absence of neutral electrolytes, gave rise to two inflexions; while in presence of salts, a single break in the potentiometric titration curves was observed. The titration curves of natural hymatomelanic acids were compared not only with the synthetic ones but also with natural and synthetic humic and fulvic acids. The titration curves did not differ essentially.

A good deal of literature has already been published on the electrochemical properties of natural and synthetic humic and fulvic acids¹⁻³. But no systematic study has so far been done on their alcohol and alkali soluble but acid insoluble hymatomelanic acid fractions. The work presented in this paper aims at obtaining information on the electrometric titrations of the natural and synthetic hymatomelanic acids and the results obtained are to be compared with known observations in this field on the natural and synthetic humic and fulvic acids¹⁻³.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. *Preparation of the samples* : Natural hymatomelanic acids were obtained from four typical Indian soils. They were designated as 'DRDN', 'PLPR', 'JBLP' and 'BRPR' corresponding to the respective place names of the soils.

Synthetic humus was prepared from persulphate oxidation and polycondensation of catechol in presence or in absence of glycine. The corresponding hymatomelanic acids were designated as 'AN' and 'A' respectively.

Synthetic humus was also prepared from hydrochloric acid polycondensation of glucose in presence or in absence of glycine. The corresponding hymatomelanic acids were designated as 'CN' and 'C' respectively.

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2. *Potentiometric titrations*: The potentiometric titrations were carried out at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.1$ with a Cambridge pH meter equipped with a Cambridge glass electrode and a saturated calomel electrode with an aqueous agar salt bridge. The electrodes were checked before each titration with buffers of pH 4.0, 7.0 and 9.1. Potentiometric titrations were carried out continuously with caustic soda in absence and in presence of 1.0 M sodium chloride. Baryta alone was also used for titration.

In order to locate more accurately the inflexion points, differential curves (not shown) for each titration have been constructed separately. Such inflexion points are shown by the arrows in the curves and the acidities corresponding to them are given in Table 1.

$p^{k_{av}}$ values were calculated from the graph corresponding to 50% neutralisation. $p^{k_{av1}}$ and $p^{k_{av2}}$ corresponding to first (-COOH) and second (Ph-OH) inflexion points respectively were also calculated from the graph.

TABLE 2
Potentiometric data

Sample	Concen- tration in %	Initial pH	pK_{uv1}	pK_{uv2}	pK_{av} (from the graph at $\alpha=0.5$)	pH at the equi- valence point							
		NaOH Ba(OH) ₂	NaOH Ba(OH) ₂	NaOH Ba(OH) ₂	NaOH Ba(OH) ₂	NaOH Ba(OH) ₂							
		NaCl	NaCl	NaCl	NaCl	NaCl							
DRDN	0.025	4.80	4.00	5.00	6.30	6.25	6.05	6.00	5.70	8.40	8.50	8.35	
PLPR	0.027	4.45	4.45	3.60	4.95	4.80	6.60	6.50	6.00	4.45	7.80	7.70	6.45
JELP	0.032	3.90	3.90	3.15	4.50	4.50	6.60	6.50	6.05	3.85	7.95	7.95	7.50
BRPR	0.033	4.00	4.00	3.20	4.90	4.80	6.90	6.50	6.10	4.20	8.00	8.25	8.10
A	0.032	4.20	4.20	3.50	5.05	4.70	6.60	6.05	6.00	4.20	7.80	7.50	6.65
AN	0.031	4.25	4.25	3.60	5.00	4.75	6.40	6.00	5.60	4.50	8.10	8.15	7.20
C	0.037	4.05	4.05	3.25	4.75	4.70	6.55	6.30	6.05	4.55	7.65	7.75	7.40
CN	0.030	4.35	4.35	3.75	5.10	4.95	6.55	6.30	5.90	4.65	7.95	7.75	7.60

3. *Conductometric titrations*: Continuous conductometric titrations were carried out with sodium hydroxide and barium hydroxide solutions using a Philips conductivity bridge in a thermostat maintained at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.1$.

DISCUSSION

The electrometric titration curves of hymatomelanic acids with bases alone always showed two breaks, the first for carboxyl and the second for phenolic hydroxyl groups, and at the same time the general features of weak acids. The potentiometric titration curves in presence of salts, showed a stronger acid behaviour and a suppression of initial *pH*. Moreover, instead of two inflexions, a single inflexion was observed³.

In conductometric titration curves, an initial drop due to carboxyl group was observed and the remaining portion of the curve resembled a weak acid character. In general, the end points could be better ascertained in the conductometric titrations than with the potentiometric titrations. The total acidity determined by the conductometric titrations was always greater than that determined by potentiometric titrations¹. The total acidities determined both by NaOH and Ba(OH)₂ were of the same order of magnitude, and the nature of the titration curves was similar to that observed by previous workers¹⁻³.

The electrochemical behaviour of synthetic hymatomelanic acids were similar to those of the natural hymatomelanic acids. The measurements were always made under comparable concentrations (Tables 2 and 3). The b.e.c. of soil hymatomelanic acids lay in the range 525 to 600 m.e., whereas the b.e.c. of synthetic varieties lay in the range 385 to 488 m.e. (Table 1).

TABLE 3

Conductometric data

Sample	Concentration in %	Specific conductance at ($\alpha = 0$) 10^5 (ohm ⁻¹ × cm ⁻¹)	Specific conductance at ($\alpha = 1$) × 10^5 (ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	
			NaOH	Ba(OH) ₂
DRDN	0.022	7.5	27.5	28.0
PLPR	0.024	8.0	30.0	29.8
JBLP	0.015	4.5	30.5	27.3
BRPR	0.026	8.8	30.3	31.0
A	0.019	6.0	21.8	21.5
AN	0.027	8.0	26.3	26.8
C	0.031	9.0	21.5	20.5
CN	0.026	8.0	21.5	21.3

The initial *pH* values, in absence of electrolytes, of soil hymatomelanic acids lay in the range of 3.90 to 4.80 which, on considering the concentration of acids, were somewhat lower than the values observed with synthetic hymatomelanic acids, viz., 4.05 to 4.35. In

presence of salts, the initial pH values attained the ranges of 3.15 to 4.00 and 3.25 to 3.75 for soil and synthetic hymatomelanic acids respectively (Table 2). The values of pK_{av} of the synthetic acids were 5.30 to 6.05 and that of the soil acids were 5.85 to 6.25. There was marked suppression of pK_{av} values on the addition of electrolytes ($\Delta pH = 0.30$ to 2.30) [Table 2].

The specific conductances of synthetic hymatomelanic acids at equivalence point of the conductometric titration varied from 20.5×10^{-5} to 26.8×10^{-5} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹, which were somewhat lower than the values observed with their soil counterparts, which lay in the range of 27.3×10^{-5} to 31.0×10^{-5} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The values of initial specific conductances lay in the ranges of 4.5×10^{-5} to 8.8×10^{-5} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 6.0×10^{-5} to 9.0×10^{-5} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹ for the natural and synthetic hymatomelanic acids respectively (Table 3)

With due attention to the concentration of acids, the initial pH values were slightly higher and the initial specific conductances were slightly lower with the synthetic hymatomelanic acids than the natural hymatomelanic acids.

Neither the aromatic/carbohydrate origin nor the incorporation of nitrogen in the structures had any marked influence on the electrochemical properties of synthetic hymatomelanic acids.

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